

Schrodinger Equation from Fokker-Planck Equation and Contradiction Due To Interference?

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In (1) it is shown how the Schrodinger equation can be “forced” in a sense to follow from the Fokker-Planck classical stochastic equation which contains a classical probability density. Other approaches in the literature which are similar use continuity equations and also a classical density. The key to all of these approaches is to assume, in an ad hoc manner it seems, that classical probability is equivalent to $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is a complex function called the wavefunction. In principle, one may write a density as $W^*(x)W(x)$. This is mathematically correct even if, for the sake of argument, it is ad hoc. The problem is that for a constant density (i.e. constant momentum and speed), one does not know if $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ or $W(x)=\exp(-ipx)$.

We consider here the arguments shown in (1). If a free particle has a density $\rho(x)=1/L$, it may be associated with $W(x) = \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$. A free particle density, however, is associated with constant p (momentum) and assumes one knows $x(t)$. If one considers the free particle to be trapped in a one-dimensional box with infinite potential walls, it travels to the right with p and then to the left with $-p$. The density $\rho(x)$ classically is $1/L$, where L is the length of the box. The density is constant in time, but the direction of motion is a function of time. Thus, information is lost considering an equation such as the Fokker-Planck equation which uses a density function which does not track the direction of motion in time. In particular, writing density $\rho(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$, which is done in (1) and applying this density to a bound particle in a box with infinite walls leads to an equation linear in $W(x)$.

Thus $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are both possible solutions if $V(x)=0$. Given that the conservation type equation obtained from the Fokker-Planck (or continuity) equation is linear in W , $\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx)$ is a solution. Thus there is interference which leads to a density which does not match a constant classical density which should apply to a particle moving to the right and then to the left in a bound state because one assumed a classical picture a priori. Simply suggesting that density classical = $W^*(x)W(x)$ mathematically does not mean that the a priori classical picture may be dropped. As a result, we argue that there exists a contradiction in approaches which write classical density as $W^*(x)W(x)$ and then obtain the Schrodinger equation.

As a remedy, we suggest that $W(x)$ does not follow from a theory of classical density= $W^*(x)W(x)$, but vice versa. One needs equation which deal with $W(x)$ a priori, and once it is found, one may create a classical density through $W^*(x)W(x)$.

Schrodinger Equation and the Fokker-Planck Equation

In (1), it is argued that the Schrodinger equation is sometimes “pulled” (our word) from the Fokker-Planck equation. (Note: (1) does not endorse this approach, but shows the calculation usually performed in the literature.) The Fokker-Planck equation from (1) is given as:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial density}(x,t) = -d/dx \{ \text{density}^*u(x,t) \} + Q(x,t) d/dx d/dx \text{density} ((1))$$

(1) then defines:

$$u_1(x,t) = u - Q \frac{d}{dx} \ln(\text{density}) \quad ((2))$$

From ((1)) and ((2)) (as discussed explicitly in (1)) one may obtain the continuity equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{density} \text{ partial} = \frac{d}{dx} \{ v(x,t) \text{ density} \} \quad ((3))$$

(Note: In the literature, one sees works which start with ((3)) a priori and do not mention the Fokker-Planck equation.)

$$v(x,t) = .5 (u + u_1) = u - .5 Q \frac{d}{dx} \ln(\text{density}) \quad ((4))$$

The procedure is then to associate:

$$\text{Density} = W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((5)) \text{ where } W(x) \text{ is a new math function}$$

$$\text{And: } v(x,t) = \hbar/2im \{ \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W) - \frac{d}{dx} \ln(W^*) \} \quad ((5))$$

Substituting ((4)) and ((5)) into the continuity equation and insisting on a linear equation yields the Schrodinger equation as argued in (1).

The Case of a Free Particle and Bound System

We wish to examine the equations above from (1) for the case of a free particle and bound system.

For a free particle, $\text{density}(x) = 1/L$ (where L is length). From ((5)) one finds that:

$$W(x) = 1/\sqrt{L} \exp(ipx) \text{ where } p \text{ is momentum (or any constant mathematically)} \quad ((6))$$

The reason we use p (momentum) for the constant is that one wishes $v = p/m$. Using $\exp(ipx)$ in ((5)) with $\hbar=1$ yields: $v = p/m$.

Thus mathematically, one may consider the classical density $= 1/L$ and link it with a mathematical function $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ or alternatively with $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}$. Thus there is ambiguity or lost information. At this point, one does not need to think about $\exp(ipx)$ as anything more than a mathematical function. The whole picture associated with the Fokker-Planck equation and the continuity equation is classical and even introducing density $= W^*(x)W(x)$ does not mean that one may drop the classical view.

Next, consider the case of $W(x)$ real. In such a case: $v(x,t) = 0$. In quantum mechanics, this is associated with a bound state. A classical bound state, however, has velocity. For example, a

particle moving back and forth in an infinite potential well has a constant density in time and space, but its velocity changes in time i.e. the direction changes. Thus a classical density for a particle moving back and forth cannot depend on x . A classical particle satisfies $E = p^2/2m + V(x)$ where $V(x) = 0$ inside the box.

Next, consider the Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

This is equivalent to classical conservation of energy with the first term on the LHS being classical kinetic energy. For $W = \exp(ipx)$ and $V(x) = 0$ one finds that: $p^2/2m = E$. The issue is that both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are solutions of ((7)) so a linear combination is also a solution, in particular:

$$W(x) = .5 (\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)) \quad ((8))$$

This solution is real and so $v(x,t) = 0$ which contradicts classical physics which should be associated with $\text{density}(x) = \text{constant}$ which is used a priori. If one starts with a classical Fokker-Planck equation, converts it into a classical continuity equation ((3)) and then introduces $\text{density} = W^*(x)W(x)$ as a mathematical procedure, one must retain classical thinking.

In fact, one may see that the problem already occurs with the definition:

$$\text{Density} = W^*(x)W(x) \quad ((9))$$

For $\text{density}(x) = \text{constant}$, $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are solutions which yield $v = p/m$ and $v = -p/m$. Thus one does not know which to use in order to create density unless one is given the extra information of "direction of motion in space". For a bound state, however, this information does not exist because the particle moves to the right part of the time and to the left the rest, but density is constant in time. Creating a linear equation in W (as described in (1)) means that if $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution, so is $\exp(-ipx)$ and also their sum. Thus a classical particle moving back and forth becomes linked with:

$$\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx) = 2 \cos(px) \quad ((10))$$

((10)) exhibits interference, but classically such interference should not exist, thus there is a contradiction. One cannot simply define $\text{density}(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ mathematically to obtain a linear differential for $W(x)$ which allows $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ solutions (due to energy conservation) because ((10)) is then a solution and this leads to a nonclassical density, yet a priori the problem is defined classically.

It is not a surprise that the linear differential equation (i.e. Schrodinger equation) obtained from the Fokker-Planck or continuity equation is linked with energy. Classical density for a bound system (particle in a well) does not distinguish between p and $-p$ and neither does an energy equation.

Resolution of the Contradiction

We argue that defining density $\text{classical}(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ is not a mathematical approach even though the equation holds. For a constant density (i.e. particle moving at a constant speed, momentum), $\exp(ipx)$ is physical and manifests itself under certain interactions linked with length because $1/p$ is proportional to a wavelength. Thus the physics of a particle moving at constant p is completely different than simply translation in space with constant probability at each x . $W(x)$ shows the direction of motion, whereas classical density does not. $W(x)$ thus contains more information than classical density, and this information is necessary we argue. Classical density only holds on average. $\exp(ipx)$ shows varying probability for different x points which contradicts constant density. Nevertheless, at each x point on average one must have conservation of energy and this is what the Schrodinger equation shows. Thus we argue that the wavefunction approach does not follow from the classical density, but vice versa. As a consequence, one should begin with $W(x)$ a priori and only use a theory which applies to $W(x)$. Later, when $W(x)$ has been found, one may calculate the classical type density $W^*(x)W(x)$ and determine its properties.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that approaches which begin with a classical density a priori and link it with a classical Fokker-Planck or continuity equation should, to be consistent, retain classical thinking throughout the derivation of the Schrodinger equation process. In particular, we show that mathematically one may consider the classical density $=1/L$ for a particle moving at a constant speed. This density does not show in which direction the particle moves, so vital information is lost. The approach used in the literature is to mathematically define: classical density $= W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is an unknown math function. One may write $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)=1$ or $W(x)=\exp(-ipx)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)=1$ so one cannot distinguish between the two directions. The approach used with classical Fokker-Planck or continuity equations is to find an equation in density (which does not contain all of the information i.e. direction of motion) and then to rewrite it as a linear equation in $W(x)$. This equation turns out to be linked with conservation of energy, thus p and $-p$ for $V(x)=0$ are both solutions. The equation is in $W(x)$, however, and linear so $\exp(ipx)+\exp(-ipx)$ is also a solution (i.e. a solution with interference). This solution, however, would never be allowed classically because the particle either moves to the right or left. The equation, however, for constant density does not distinguish this and so breaks the classical picture which was the a priori assumption. No reason is given for breaking the classical view and so we argue that such an approach is inconsistent.

We argue instead that one cannot consider a priori a classical density. The a priori "probability" is $W(x)$ and one needs to find equations associated with it, because it describes completely different physics and contains information on direction which classical density does not as well as information about momentum. For example, classically the density is constant for

a particle with constant speed, but this does not distinguish direction or even the magnitude of momentum. Thus we argue that $W(x)$ represents a more complete physical description, but at the same time maps into the lower information classical probability picture.

Reference

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